

Larvicidal Activity of Some Congolese Plant Extracts against *Anopheles Gambiae*

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ABSTRACT

Aqueous extracts from leaves of four Congolese plants species were tested for their larvicidal activity against *Anopheles gambiae* mosquitoes by exposing early 4th instar larvae to a series of concentrations of these plants extracts. Mortality counts were made after 24 hours exposure. Larvicidal effects were found for *Canarium schweinfurthii* Engl, *Lippia multiflora* Moldenke and *Annona senegalensis* Pers with LC50 values of 2.0, 25.1 and 30.2 mg/l respectively. A chemical screening was done on these active plants indicating the presence of alkaloids and polyphenols probable responsible of this activity. *Morinda morindoides* extract showed no toxicity on larvae.

Keyword: Larvicidal activity, plant extracts, *Anopheles gambiae*, Congolese plants.

INTRODUCTION:

Mosquitoes-borne diseases, such as malaria are still major public health problem in the South- East Asian, and in many African countries because of their tropical or subtropical climate [1-4]. Although chemical vector control programs have been carried on for long time, the prevalence of mosquito-vector (*Anopheles gambiae*) diseases remains high because of the refusal by householders to house spraying with synthetic insecticides, changes in biting habits of vectors and evolution of mosquito resistance to conventional insecticides [2-4].

Search for new control agents from natural products such as plant secondary metabolites has gained popularity among researchers in countries with a strong herbal tradition and a large number of plants have been reported to possess insecticidal activity [1,5-7]. Several plant extracts and isolated compounds from different plant families have been reported for their insecticidal properties [7]. Studies on natural products from medicinal plants as larvicides have indicated that they could provide an alternative to synthetic products used as insecticides [5-7]. Currently limonoids such as azadirachtin and gedunin, present in species of Meliaceae and Rutaceae, are recognized for their toxic effects on insects and are used in several insecticide formulations in many part of the world [8].

In Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), malaria remains an important public health problem and causes loss of economic activity. In addition, the poverty of Congolese population has led them to search for other modes of treatment like the use of medicinal plants with repellent or insecticidal properties [9-12].

In fact, DRC is by far the African country with the highest biodiversity and his flora is among the richest in the world. Indeed, this country contains a large area of Congo basin forest reputed for the extraordinary richness of its flora and boasts a wide variety of medicinal plants species [10, 13-19]. Some studies were

done on Congolese medicinal plants [13-26] and some of them were dedicated to plant with antimalarial activity [9-12].

But scientific studies on Congolese plants with insecticidal activity are still scarce. This study aims to find low cost alternatives for the control of mosquito vectors by evaluating the larvicidal activity of some Congolese plant species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mosquitoes

The mosquito species used for the tests was *Anopheles gambiae*. These mosquitoes were reared in the laboratory of the Department of Environment, Faculty of sciences, Kinshasa University, Democratic Republic of Congo. Late 3rd - early 4th instar larvae of *Anopheles gambiae* were used to screen the larvicidal activity of extracts obtained from four plants species.

Plant collection

Leaves of four plants species (*Annona senegalensis* Pers, *Canarium schweinfurthii* Engl, *Morinda morindoides* Back, *Lippia multiflora* Moldenke) were collected from various areas of Kinshasa regions. These wild specimens were identified at the herbarium of sciences Faculty, University of Kinshasa.

Preparation of extracts

Leaves of these four plants were dried in the shade, cut up and then ground in a homogenizer. The powder material from each species was macerated at room temperature for two days and then filtered through whatman filter paper. The resulting crude extracts were kept at 25° C until screening for their larvicidal activity.

Larvicidal test

Methods for testing larvicidal effect of the crude extracts were modified from those of World Health Organization [4].

Twenty healthy late third to early fourth instar larvae were introduced into each testing cup, which contained 100 ml of

deionized water. A measured volume of stock solution was added to obtain the desired concentrations. Experiments were carried out with a series of four concentrations, each with four replicates, with a final total number of 80 larvae for each concentration. Each batch of replicates contained one control of 100ml of water alone

and another of 100ml water containing a volume of powder extract tested. After 24 hours exposures the dead larvae were counted. The mortality was recorded after 24 hour of exposure as lethal concentration (LC).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 give used plants and their family

Family	Scientific binomial name	Vernacular name	Used Part
Annonaceae	<i>Annona senegalensis</i> Pers	Kilolo, Mulolo (Kikongo) Bonenge na esobe (lingala)	Leaves
Burseraceae	<i>Canarium schweinfurthii</i> Engl.	Bidi, Mpafu (Kikongo)	Leaves
Rubiaceae	<i>Morinda morindoides</i> Back	Kongo bololo (lingala) Kilulu kundju (Swahili)	Leaves
Verbenacea	<i>Lippia multiflora</i> Moldenke	Bulukutu (kikongo, Nyemba Lubwitshi (tshiluba)	Leaves

This table gives four plants belonging to four families. *Morinda morindoides* is a well-known antimalarial plant in Congolese traditional medicine and the three others are known for their different usages [24-26].

Larvicidal activity of aqueous extracts plant against *Anopheles gambiae*.

Results of the screening of larvicidal activity of the selected plants are given in table2.

Table 2. Larvicidal activity of aqueous extracts of plants against *A. gambiae*

Plant	Larvicidal activity (mg/l)		
	LC50	LC90	LC99
<i>Canarium schweinfurthii</i>	2.0 ±0.5	5.1±1.0	8.0±1.8
<i>Lippia multiflora</i>	25.1±2.7	86.3±5.2	98.3±6.8
<i>Annona senegalensis</i>	30.2±4.3	145.1±11.5	200.0±21.3
<i>Morinda morindoides</i>	-	-	-

Legend: -LC50: Lethal concentration required to kill 50 % of larvae

-LC90: Lethal concentration required to kill 90 % of larvae

-LC99: Lethal concentration required to kill 99 % of larvae

Among those plants, *Canarium schweinfurthii* was found to have very high larvicidal activity with 6 hour LC50 values of 2.0 mg/l. Its LC90 and LC99, were obtained at 5.1 mg/l and 8.0 mg/l. *Lippia multiflora* and *Annona senegalensis* showed also high larvicidal activity with 24 hours LC50 values of respectively 25.1 and 30.2 mg/l. Indeed, extracts of LC50 < 50mg/l are generally classified as having a very higher larvicidal activity [5-8, 27]. But *Morinda morindoides* shows no toxic effect on *A. gambiae* larvae. After a period of 24 hours, the mortality counts were performed. The mortality percent of larvae is shown in figure 1.

Fig.1. Mortality rate average of larvae at different concentrations of plant extracts.

Figure 1 shows a mortality rate of 100% for all used concentrations from 25mg/l to 100mg/l for *Canarium schweinfurthii*. For *Lippia multiflora* and *Annona senegalensis* aqueous extracts, the mortality rate percentage increases with the concentration. This confirms the very high activity of *Canarium schweinfurthii*. In fact, Sawadago [28] showed that *C. schweinfurthii* leaves extracts possess a high bacteriological activity in skin germs, but larvicidal effect of this plant have not yet been screened.

Chemical screening of the three plants

Chemical screening results of the three active plants are shown in table 3.

All the four plants contain polyphenols (flavonoids, anthocyanins, leucoanthocyanins and tanins) and alkaloids. *Canarium schweinfurthii* contains little more metabolites than *Annona senegalensis* and *Lippia multiflora*. Quinones are only in *Annona senegalensis* when saponins are only in *Canarium schweinfurthii*. These results confirm those of Mpiana et al [25] that found the presence of the same natural compounds in *A. senegalensis* extracts and those of Bissangou [29] and Kunle [30] for *Lippia multiflora*

According to Sunita and al [31] study on the effects of extracts *Ayapa triplinervis* against larvae of three insect pests of horticultural crops, alkaloids and tannins are chemical groups having greater food deterrence in larvae of *Plutella xylostella* and *Crociodolomia binotulis* followed by phenols and flavonoids. Liu et al [32] considered alkaloids among the active molecules against *Culicidae* mosquitoes larvae.

As it can be found in table 3, all these chemical groups are present in the three plants under study. This indicates that the larvicidal activity of these plants would be due to alkaloids and polyphenols in general and to tannins in particular.

Table 3. Presence of chemical groups in the plants under study.

N°	Secondary metabolites	Plants		
		<i>A. senegalensis</i>	<i>L. multiflora</i>	<i>C. schweinfurthii</i>
1	Polyphénols	+	+	+
	- Flavonoids	+	+	+
	- Anthocyanins	+	+	+
	- Leucoanthocyanins	+	+	+
	- Tanins	+	+	+
	- Quinones	+	-	-
2	Alkaloids	+	+	+
3	Saponins	-	-	+
4	Triterpenoids	+	-	+
5	Steroids	-	+	+

Legend:

+: presence of metabolite
-: absence of metabolite

CONCLUSION

The present study reveals that the aqueous extracts of *Canarium schweinfurthii*, *Annona senegalensis* and *Lippia multiflora* have a very high toxic effect on *Anopheles gambiae* larvae with LC50 < 50 mg/l when *Morinda morindoides* extracts show no toxicity. The highest activity was found for *C. schweinfurthii* extracts. This activity would be due to alkaloids and polyphenols like tannins. Extraction of these compounds and their larvicidal activity tests are under study.

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